

INSTABILITY OF SANDWICH BEAMS AND COLUMNS WITH FRP FACINGS

Ori Ishai
Associate Professor
Department of Mechanics
Technion - Israel Institute of Technology
Haifa, Israel

Aharon Saggi
Materials and Processes Engineering Division
Israel Aircraft Industries
Lod, Israel

Sandwich beams and columns composed of an aluminum honeycomb core and glass- or carbon-fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP, CFRP) facing, were tested under compressive and flexural loading up to failure. The main objectives were: (a) study of the mechanisms prevailing during the local and general buckling modes of the above systems, versus their conventional sandwich counterparts made of ductile isotropic metals; (b) experimental examination of the validity, for *orthotropic* facing, of theories originally derived for predicting instability of sandwiches with *isotropic* facing.

Findings can be summarized as follows:

(a) Most sandwich columns failed through general buckling or compressive fracture of the facing, transition between the modes depending on the slenderness and thickness parameters of the column.

(b) Local buckling (wrinkling) of the facing was not observed visually, but was found indirectly to prevail below a certain facing-to-core thickness ratio (too low for practical application in the case of CFRP's).

(c) Existing expressions for general buckling values of conventional sandwich columns may be adapted for orthotropic facing by substituting the longitudinal modulus of elasticity for the isotropic one.

1. Introduction

Sandwich structures are accepted as the most efficient elements in aviation applications where low weight and high mechanical performance are vital; the structures most commonly used in this context comprise aluminum honeycomb cores and aluminum facings. High-performance composite materials such as carbon- or boron-fiber reinforced plastics, which are superior to aluminum in terms of specific strength and stiffness - have high potential as sandwich facings, but their widespread use is still limited for the following reasons:

(a) High-performance FRP composites are brittle and highly orthotropic; this makes for low toughness and for high sensitivity to stress concentrations and to localized transverse impacts, compared with the isotropic and ductile structural metals.

(b) Testing techniques for characterization of orthotropic FRP's are relatively new and complex (especially considering the numerous parameters involved), and moreover entail relatively high scatter and low confidence levels, at the same time. Insufficient practical experience is available for verifying the engineering validity of the present methods of analysis.

(c) Fabrication technology is mainly manual, making for non-uniformity in the final product.

Most data and analyses on sandwich structures to-date [1], [2], refer to isotropic ductile component materials and are thus inapplicable directly in the design of sandwich structures with orthotropic brittle FRP facings.

One of the most critical problems in aircraft sandwich design is performance of the thin-wall facings under compressive stresses, produced directly through compressive loading or indirectly through flexural or torsional loading. Under such loading modes, the main problem is structural instability, generally classified as follows:

- (a) general buckling
- (b) local facing buckling (wrinkling)
- (c) intercellular facing buckling (dimpling)
- (d) core shear buckling (crimpling)
- (e) simultaneous compressive failure of the facing material.

The present work deals with instability of FRP sandwich columns and beams, with the following main objectives:

- (a) study of the mechanism of general and local buckling modes of FRP's commonly used as sandwich facing materials;
- (b) study of the instability failure mechanism of sandwich structures with brittle, orthotropic, FRP facings, versus their

ductile isotropic aluminum counterparts;

(c) experimental verification of the relevance, for facing materials, of theories formulated for predicting critical buckling loads in sandwiches composed of isotropic ductile materials.

2. Analytical Considerations

Most of the solutions for general and local buckling of sandwich columns are available in literature on sandwich panels.

2.1 General Buckling.

The common expression for predicting the critical buckling load in sandwich columns with thin isotropic facings ($t \ll c$) under axial compression (Figure 1), is eq. 1 (1,2,3).

$$P_{cr} = \frac{k^2 \pi^2 E_f t c^2 / 2L^2}{1 + [k^2 \pi^2 E_f t c / 2L^2 G_c]} \quad (1)$$

- where:
- P_{cr} - critical buckling load per unit width (b)
 - E_f - Young's modulus of facing
 - t - facing thickness
 - c - core thickness
 - G_c - shear modulus of core
 - L - column length
 - k - coefficient for different boundary conditions:
 - $k = 1$ for hinged ends
 - $k = 2$ for fixed ends

For orthotropic facings, it is suggested that E_f for the isotropic case be replaced by E_{xx} - the axial modulus of the column facings.

Equation 1 may be rewritten in terms of the critical facing stress (σ_{cr}) at buckling, as follows:

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{k^2 \pi^2 E_f / 4\lambda^2}{1 + k^2 \pi^2 E_f \alpha / 2\lambda^2 G_c} \quad (2)$$

- where: $\lambda = L/c$ is the slenderness-ratio of the column and $\alpha = t/c$ the facing/core thickness ratio

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_f / 4}{\lambda^2 + \pi^2 E_f \alpha / 2G_c} \quad (\text{for hinged ends}) \quad (2.1)$$

2.2 Local Instability

Wrinkling is a mode mainly dependent on the facing material and on its geometric characteristics. The classic solution for wrinkling of a sandwich with a continuous core was given by Hoff and co-workers [1], [2], and is based on the model of a beam on an elastic foundation. The wrinkling stress for isotropic core and facings is given by:

$$\sigma_{wr} = K_1 E_f^{1/3} E_c^{1/3} G_c^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

where E_c is Young's modulus of the core.

For the case of a honeycomb core, an analytic expression based on the work of Norris et al. [5], is quoted in MIL-HDBK-23 [4] as follows:

$$\sigma_{wr} = \frac{0.82 [E_c t / \eta E_f]^{1/2} \eta E_f}{1 + 0.64 K_\delta} \quad (4)$$

where

$$K_\delta = \frac{\delta E_c}{c F_c} \quad (\text{Ref. [6]}) \quad (5)$$

η - plasticity reduction factor

F_c - minimum flatwise sandwich strength

δ - amplitude of initial waviness in facing (in inches)

For orthotropic brittle facings such as boron-epoxy, an averaged effective modulus is proposed instead of E_f ,

$$\bar{E}_f = \sqrt{E_x E_y} \quad (6)$$

(where E_x and E_y are the axial and transverse facing moduli respectively) and the factor η is assumed to equal 1 [7].

Recently, use of an upper bound to eq. (4) was suggested [8], based on the assumption of no initial waviness ($\delta = 0$):

$$\sigma_{wr}^+ = 0.82 (\alpha)^{1/2} (E_c \bar{E}_f)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

This expression is in agreement with theoretical solutions obtained by other authors [9] and with earlier experimental data [5,6].

In more recent works [10], a special effort was made to solve the problem of general buckling and local instability of sandwich panels with laminated composite facings. In an experimental study of CFRP facings [11], no definite location could be obtained for wrinkling loads, possibly due to compressive failure of the facing prior to (or simultaneously with) the wrinkling stage.

3. Experimental

The main requirements for high mechanical performance of a sandwich are:

- (a) strong and stiff facings;
- (b) low weight;
- (c) core with reasonable shear strength and compressive stiffness perpendicular to the facing plane.

3.1 Material Systems

Three types of fibers were used in facings of unidirectional and cross-ply fiber reinforced epoxy - E glass, S glass, and HTS carbon, with aluminum facings (2024-T3) as reference material. Aluminum honeycomb (Hexcell) was used for the sandwich core. (For specifications, see Tables 1 - 3).

The mechanical properties of the facing specimens were measured in the axial direction (x) (see Figure 2).

3.2 Preparation of Sandwich Specimens

Facing laminates of S glass and HTS carbon fibers were prepared by hot compression of "prepreg" FRP sheets, according to the manufacturer's instructions. E glass reinforced laminates were prepared by wet lay-up. (Volume fiber content 49-51% for hardened CFRP laminates, 54-56% for hardened GRP laminates).

The hardened laminates were bonded to the honeycomb core by Metlbond 328 adhesive (Narmco).

Sandwich panels were cut in the shape of beams and columns, and flexible epoxy was injected at the ends to prevent failure in the compression zone. The column specimens were also provided with special tabs (see Figure 3) for two purposes: (a) to reduce stress concentrations at the loading ends and (b) to ensure satisfactory fixing and hinging of the ends.

Electrical strain gauges were glued to the facing surfaces in the two major directions (x and y).

3.3 Testing Procedure

Loading was carried out on an Instron tester. Surface strains were measured with an x-y recorder, axial strains - with an Instron standard extensometer, and lateral deflections - with a special device based on the strain-gauge extensometer.

3.3.1 Compressive Failure Test. The test was conducted on short columns axially-loaded in compression, and on beams loaded in flexure, with a view to determining the compressive strength of the facing.

3.3.2 Compressive Stability Test. Specimens were axially loaded in compression, with loads and axial and lateral strains recorded simultaneously. At first, 30% of the ultimate load was applied as a check on load centricity and on coordination of the recording process. The second stage (50% of the ultimate) yielded data for determination of the elastic parameters. Only in the third stage was the specimen loaded up to failure.

3.3.3 Flexure Test. A special device for applying four-point flexure (Figure 4) was used with the beam specimens. The first stage was again carried out at 30% of the ultimate, with loads and axial and lateral strains recorded simultaneously.

The second stage consisted in loading up to failure, with loads and central deflections recorded simultaneously.

4. Test Results

4.1 Compressive Strength Data (Table 4)

Scatter is relatively small (coefficient of variation below 10%), and there is good agreement with regard to the ultimate compressive stress between the compression and flexure tests.

Stress-strain curves are mostly linear, terminating in catastrophic failure (Figure 5), with the fracture surface inclined to the specimen axis. A typical fractured compressive specimen (CFRP) is shown in Figure 6.

4.2 General Buckling Data (Table 5)

The series comprised 128 specimens covering full ranges of material and geometrical variables. Scatter is small in most cases and critical stresses are in good agreement with theoretical prediction.

Typical axial stress versus time, and load versus lateral deflection curves for CFRP columns in compression are shown in

Figure 7. The point of instability is clearly seen and coincides for the axial and lateral recordings.

Strain-gauge data for the facings are more sensitive and show divergence between the axial strains (ϵ_1 and ϵ_2) at the instability level (Figure 8).

4.3 Local Instability Tests (Table 6)

The series comprises about 75 specimens. Scatter is within reasonable limits. Significantly, in most cases there is no direct evidence of a specific failure mechanism. There is no indication of wrinkling or dimpling, and attempts to detect them by high-speed photography failed. Subsequent indirect analysis of the results led to the hypothesis that owing to the high brittleness of the CFRP facing, local wrinkling spontaneously progressed into fracture. There is again good agreement between compression and flexure tests.

5. Discussion

In classical design of columns, the optimal situation for a given structural requirement is seen where all failure modes are approaches simultaneously. Recently, a new design philosophy has emerged especially where lightweight and orthotropic composite materials are considered. From a more fundamental viewpoint, however, it is important to define regions in which a certain mode predominates, or limits within which two or three modes are active and beyond which a shift from one mode to another is evident.

In sandwich structures, optimal performance is achieved when the facing strength is fully utilized. The latter is, accordingly, the main design parameter, and its relationship to other instability failure modes determines the range of efficient utilization of the whole structure.

5.1 General Buckling versus Compressive Failure

5.1.1 Failure Modes. General buckling is characterized by sudden lateral sagging of the column at the critical load (unaccompanied by spontaneous fracture). This critical point is followed by a plateau up to failure (Figure 7).

In the case of CFRP and GRP facings, unloading of the columns beyond the critical load resulted in total recovery of the axial deformations. By contrast, residual deformations were detected in the case of aluminum facings, apparently due to the plastic nature of the metal.

In columns with high slenderness ratio, eccentricity manifested in differential straining of the facings (Figure 8) is unavoidable.

5.1.2 Effect of Sandwich Parameters on Critical Stress for General Buckling. Plots of the critical stress vs. slenderness ratio for different thickness-ratio values (Figure 9) show very good agreement between experimental findings and the theoretical predictions of eq. (2).

The upper limit for general buckling coincides with the compressive failure stress level (σ_{uc}), and the limiting slenderness ratio (λ_0) for a given thickness ratio (α) is obtainable analytically by equating σ_{uc} with σ_{cr} in eq. (2).

$$\lambda_0 = \left[\frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{E_f}{\sigma_{uc}} - \frac{\pi^2}{2} \frac{E_f}{G_c} \alpha \right]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

As is seen from Figures 10 and 11, and eq. (8), the λ_0 vs. α relationship is represented by parabolic curves which tend to a straight line with increasing core stiffness.

5.2 Local Instability (Wrinkling) and Compressive Failure

The experimental data in Table 6 are compared in Figure 12 with the upper-limit theoretical prediction for the wrinkling stress according to eq. (7). Over most of the range, the experimental critical stress coincides with the compressive strength level, and is independent of the thickness ratio.

There exists a limiting thickness ratio (α_0) above which compressive failure predominates, and below which a marked decrease of the critical stress occurs. In this range, the σ_{cr} vs. α relationship roughly follows the prediction of eq. (7) with an upward shift of about 20%. The assumed wrinkling effect predominates at very low thickness ratios ($\alpha < 0.02$) so that only the compressive-failure modes need be considered. Even where wrinkling was expected, it could not be detected visually in brittle composites such as unidirectional CFRP where even a slight tendency to wrinkling causes local flexural stresses which result in sudden local compressive fracture of the facings.

6. Summary and Conclusions

The following conclusions may be drawn regarding general buckling and local instability of sandwich columns and beams:

6.1 Three modes of failure are distinguishable - compressive failure of facings, general buckling of column, and local insta-

bility of facings.

6.2 The general buckling load is detectable by the following means: recording of axial stress vs. time; measurement of axial strains, and recording of axial load vs. lateral deflection.

6.3 Local instability (wrinkling) is unobservable visually in brittle FRP materials, but detectable indirectly in analysis of the experimental data.

6.4 There is good agreement between experimental data and analytical prediction for isotropic facings as regards the critical stress in the general buckling tests. Accordingly, the theories for general buckling of sandwich columns with isotropic facings are valid for predicting the behavior of sandwiches with orthotropic ones, with the longitudinal (axial) modulus of the facing replacing the isotropic one.

6.5 The critical stress for general buckling decreases with increasing slenderness ratios. Below a limiting level (λ_0) compressive failure of the facing predominates, and the failure stress of the column no longer depends on its geometry.

6.6 There is good agreement between compressive failure data for the facing, obtained in compression and flexure tests.

6.7 Local instability (wrinkling) of the facings on CFRC sandwich columns and beams is confined to very low thickness ratios, impractical for most structural uses. The wrinkling stress depends mainly, in fact, on the thickness ratio; a limiting ratio (α_0) exists, above which compressive failure predominates and failure of the sandwich is independent of the geometrical and stiffness parameters of the components.

6.8 Existing theories for wrinkling of sandwiches with ductile and isotropic facings cannot be used for predicting the local-instability critical stress in sandwiches with brittle orthotropic FRP facings without experimental checking.

Nomenclature

- b - sandwich width
- t - thickness of sandwich facing
- c - thickness of sandwich core
- k - coefficient of different boundary conditions
- P - axial load per sandwich unit width
- P_{cr} - critical buckling per buckling load unit width

- E_f - Young's Modulus of sandwich facing
 E_c - Young's Modulus of sandwich core
 G_c - shear modulus of sandwich core
 L - sandwich column length
 F_c - minimum flatwise sandwich strength
 K_δ - wrinkling factor
 ω - wavelength of initial facing deflection
 $\lambda = L/c$ - sandwich slenderness ratio
 $\alpha = t/c$ - facing to core thickness ratio
 σ_{wr} - facing wrinkling stress
 σ_{cr} - column buckling critical stress
 η - plasticity reduction factor
 δ - amplitude of initial facing waviness
 θ - fiber orientation angle

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TABLE I: Mechanical Properties of Fibers and Matrix Components of the Sandwich Facings.

Matrix		Product specification	Young's Modulus	Tensile strength	Specific gravity	Designation
Epoxy	Hardener		msi	ksi	gr/cm ³	
ERLA 4617	DDM	Union Carbide	0.6-0.7	20.0	1.25	Matrix A
EPON 828	ZZL	Shell	~0.5	12.0	1.17	Matrix B
Fibers						
Carbon (HTS)		Unidirectional prepreg sheet	32-40	300-400	1.75	HCF
E glass		Unidirectional 1543 fabric	10.5	280-360	2.49	EGF
S glass		Scotch-ply 1009-26S (3M)	12.5	450-550	2.55	SGF

I. Mechanical Properties of Fibers and Matrix Components of the Sandwich Facings.

TABLE II: Mechanical Characteristics of Composite Facing.

No.	Material System		Fiber Orientation	Axial Young's Modulus	Axial Strength
	Fibers	Matrix	θ	msi	ksi
1	HCF	A	0	18	170
2	HCF	A	0 - 90°	9	90
3	SGF	Not specified	0	6.5	140
4	EGF	B	0	5.5	120
5	EGF	B	0 - 90°	3.5	65
6	Aluminum 2024 T3			10.0	50

II. Mechanical Characteristics of Composite Facing.

TABLE III: Effective Mechanical Properties of Core Materials. (Fig. 1)

Hexcell Honeycomb Designation	Normal stiffness in z direction	Shear stiffness in x-y plane	Normal strength in z direction	Shear strength in x-y plane
[ref:12]	[ksi]	[ksi]	[psi]	[psi]
3/16 - 5052-	75	46	290	210
3/16 - 5052-0015	145	68	525	330
1/4 - 5052-0015	86	48	340	235
1/4 - 5052-004	340	130	1420	700

III. Effective Mechanical Properties of Core Materials (Fig. 1)

TABLE IV: Facing Compressive Strength Data (obtained from sandwich testing).

Test Mode	No. of specimens	Facing thickness ratio $a=t/c[10^{-2}]$	Average failure stress [ksi]	Standard of deviation [ksi]	Coefficient variation [%]
Flexure	10	2.16	172	7.9	4.6
Flexure	100	4.35	174	22	12.6
Flexure	5	5.0	166	8	5.9
Compression	2	5.3	180		
Compression	12	1.70	176	8.3	5.0
Compression	12	3.0	178	8.2	4.8

IV. Facing Compressive Strength Data (obtained from sandwich testing).

TABLE V: General Buckling Test Results.

Material System Table 2	No. of specimens.	Thick-ness ratio. $\alpha=t/c$ [10^{-2}]	Slender-ness ratio. $\lambda=l/c$	Clamp-ing conditions.	Facing's Young's Modulus. E [msi]	Core ef-fective shear modulus. G_c [ksi]	Critical stress σ_{cr} [ksi]	
							Exper. average value.	Calculated value [eq. 2]
1	5	1.14	8	hinged	18	30	170	
	6	1.45	6.6	"	18	30	173	
	2	3.45	13.5	"	18	45	190	188
	2	3.45	29.0	"	18	45	57	56
	2	3.45	40.0	"	18	45	29	30
	2	3.45	50.0	"	18	45	190	19.2
	2	3.45	24	fixed	18	45	190	221
	2	3.45	40	"	18	45	100	101
	2	3.45	50	"	18	45	67	68.5
	4	5.75	25	"	18	45	180	160
	3	5.75	21	"	18	45	180	220
	7	5.75	28	hinged	18	45	53	55
	3	5.75	37	"	18	45	32	33.5
	4	5.75	47	"	18	45	21	22
	2	8.25	58	"	18	45	15	14
2	2	9.2	28	hinged	8	45	31	30
	2	9.2	39	"	8	45	16	15
	2	9.2	53	"	8	45	8.8	9.1
	4	9.2	59	"	8	45	7.5	7.4
3	3	6.9	28.6	fixed	6.5	45	60	65
	1	6.9	21	hinged	6.5	45	32	32
	2	6.9	24	"	6.5	45	24	25
	3	6.9	37	"	6.5	45	11	11.3
4	4	6.9	28	hinged	5.0	45	20	19
5	1	5.2	25.5	hinged	10.0	45	40	40
	4	5.2	29.5	"	10.0	45	28	29
	2	5.2	48.0	"	10.0	45	11	11.5
	2	5.2	53.0	"	10.0	45	10	9.5
	1	5.2	59.0	"	10.0	45	8	7.7

V. General Buckling Test Results.

TABLE VI: Data of Tests Conducted for Determination of Facing Local Buckling Stress in Unidirectional CFRP Sandwich Columns and Beams.

No. of specimens	Core effective Young's Modulus	Facing thickness	Core's thickness	Thickness ratio	Loading mode	Failure Stress σ_u [ksi]		Standard derivation	Coefficient of variation
						Exper. aver. value	Calculated value (upper bound) eq. 7		
N	E_c [ksi]	t [mm]	c [mm]	$\alpha=t/c$ [10^{-2}]			ksi	%	
4	86	0.25	25.4	1	compress.	100	79	-	-
6	86	0.25	25.4	1	flexure	160	79	8.2	4.95
17	86	0.44	25.4	1.65	flexure	170	102	8.3	4.85
12	86	0.33	19	1.74	flexure	165	120	8.5	5.10
4	86	0.33	19	1.74	compress.	170	120	-	-
20	86	0.55	25.4	2.16	flexure	172	139	7.9	4.6
4	86	0.44	19	2.46	compress.	180	144	-	-
4	86	0.33	9.75	3	compress.	180	170	-	-
4	340	0.66	12.7	5.2	flexure	182	400	-	-

VI. Data of Tests Conducted for Determination of Facing Local Buckling Stress in Unidirectional CFRP Sandwich Columns and Beams.

1. Schematic illustration of sandwich element.

2. Lay-up of fibers in unidirectional (a) and cross-ply (b) facing laminates.

3. Typical column specimens with special end tabs for fixed (a) and hinged (b) boundary conditions.

4. Flexural test for sandwich beam specimen.

5. Typical stress vs strain in compression test for short CFRP sandwich column up to failure.

6. Typical compressive failure of CFRP sandwich column specimen.

7. Load vs time (axial deformation) vs transverse deflection for CFRP sandwich columns under axial compression loading.

8. Facing axial strain vs time (axial deformation) for CFRP sandwich columns under axial compressive loading.

9. The effect of slenderness ratio on critical stress for general buckling of CFRP sandwich columns in compression.

10. Limit slenderness ratio (λ_0) as a function of thickness-ratio for CFRP sandwich columns composed of different core moduli (G_c). (Eq. 8).

11. Limit slenderness ratio (λ_0) as a function of thickness-ratio for sandwich columns composed of different facing stiffness (E_f) and same core stiffness. (Eq. 8).

12. Critical compression stress as a function of thickness ratio in CFRC sandwich columns and beams (based on local instability tests data given in Table 6).